

PHILOSOPHY

SOCIAL ADVERTISING IN THE STRUCTURE OF COMMUNICATIVE ACTIVITY OF SOCIETY

Koval V.

*Postgraduate student of the Department of Philosophy
Zhytomyr State University named after Ivan Franko*

Zhytomyr, Ukraine

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7469-4119

Abstract

Purpose. The study aims to study the place of social advertising in the structure of communicative activities, its impact on the interaction of social actors, identifying factors of social advertising and how society and people respond to this type of communication and how it affects their social development. Social advertising is a means of disclosure and acceptance, attracting attention and influencing the internal processes of society. In the structure of communicative activity, it plays the role of a consolidator and reveals the acute themes of man in society, helping to achieve socially useful goals and promote universal values.

Keywords: communicative activity, social advertising, social communication, advertising, society, communication.

Introduction. The information society has a complex communicative structure that is constantly changing, as a result of which the individual must constantly adapt. Due to the dynamic changes of the cultural, ideological, social environment, people change their orientations and values for their own adaptation in the modern world. In the process of development of society in some of its parts there are problematic actions that harm the freedoms, values, interests of a person or group of people. These problems can become widespread within society, which they often ignore, increasing the problem and encouraging its rooting in the structure of intersubjective communications. Using free communication, individuals can present their own problems or conflicts with society to the public, but the problem of a group of people is a problem for society. General statistics show that society's values and interests are variable and depend on many factors, including communication. Having existed for a long time with such a problem, society can resort to the process of self-defense, when the existing problem is referred to the target audience of society, in order to eradicate it and promote universal values. Social advertising - the type of information that ensures the achievement of social and human goals, paying attention to the problem point in society and ways to solve it. Social advertising occupies an important place in intersubjective communication, acting as an element of balance in addressing socially important issues of interaction between people. This article examines the place of social advertising in the structure of communicative activities.

The study of social advertising in various manifestations of social reality and the relationship with the communicative activities of society has attracted and still attracts the attention of many researchers. Social and foreign researchers, in particular, have made a significant contribution to the study of tolerance as a normative practice of conflict resolution: Agarkov O. A., Davydkina I. B., Dmitrieva L. M., Doktorovich M. O., Yermakova Z. I., Orban-Lembrick L. E., Sidorenko T. , Uchenova V., V. Havkina L., Grubin O., Shal'man T. M, Ushkvarok, D., Holodna, A., Shinkarenko, I.

Goal. The aim of the study is to study the places of social advertising in the structure of communicative activities, to identify factors of social advertising and how society responds to this type of communication, to ensure their interests and values. Identify the causes and ways of expressing social advertising of social reality.

Presenting main material. Analyzing the process of communication is the exchange of information and emotions at different levels. Due to the passage through the prism of complex human and social structures, it is a more complex process of information management: exchange, processing, formation, refinement, development and change of information. Each micro-process with information embodies the concept of "communication" as the main in modern human life. The concept of "communication" has become an important feature of the modern information society. The communicative activity of society is manifested in all spheres of human life and groups of people. These are interpersonal, intergroup, interinstitutional communication, mass communication, etc. Man is both a consumer and creator of information and this is manifested in communicative activities.

According to Orban-Lembrick, "Communication presupposes the existence of a single communicative space; participants in communication are active subjects of mutual information "[Orban-Lembrick, 2010]. In today's information society, communication is a unifying factor in society, due to the creation of a single communicative space and active participation in global communication. The structure of the communicative activity of society is based on the fact that each person is both a consumer and creator of information. Due to the technical development of society, it has become global.

Society actively interacts with each other at all communicative levels, which gives rise to different types of social communication. Social communication is the exchange between people or other social actors of integral symbolic messages, which reflect information, knowledge, ideas, emotions, etc., due to a number of socially significant assessments, specific situations, communicative spheres and norms of communication

adopted in a particular society [Yermakova, 2011]. Processes are characterized by increasing dynamism and complexity of social, economic, industrial, scientific processes, which in turn increases the amount of information that interacts between actors. In this way, there is a greater cohesion of interests and at the same time information independence of the subjects, as there is a choice between the choice of information. Against this background, there is conflict, leadership and oppression of certain categories of the population.

Society is actively developing in ideological, communicative, cultural terms, so the rapid transformation of people causes different worldviews, which in interaction with others, often causes conflict situations at the domestic, cultural, ideological, social levels. Due to the multiple phenomena of this situation, there are social problems associated with various reasons: from the rejection of small household changes and to complete hatred of certain categories of the population. As society's communication capabilities increase, it is possible to pay attention to problems, solve them, and create even more tension. Social advertising is one of the types of solving social problems, a way to draw attention and promote certain ideas to people. Social advertising aims to influence society by changing its moods and attitudes to certain issues. Our society is plastic, able to accept certain ideas and alienate themselves from others. As a result of gradual and planned influence, it is possible to change the standards of people's behavior and their attitude to certain problems. M. Doktorovich in his study notes that there are two levels of social advertising: 1) tactical, in which advertising is designed to introduce or establish specific rules and regulations, purpose: the proposal of a set of actions, tactical move, algorithmization of activities in a given situation; 2) strategic, the orientation of the advertising message on the formation of a strategic attitude to life, the world, creates the desired "image" of the world, purpose: to consolidate existing or proposed moral and behavioral norms [Doktorovich, 2014]. From the point of view of practical use, the tactical level is focused on creating an image and a call to action, and the strategic level is focused on consolidating statements from social messages.

Social advertising is a type of communication focused on drawing attention to current issues of society and its moral values. Accordingly, the mission of social advertising is to change the behavioral model of society. Social advertising is an effective means of combating social evil. It changes people's attitude to everyday reality, followed by changes in behavior and the formation of new social values [Doktorovich, 2014]. LM Dmitrieva defines social advertising as a type of public communication using tools and methods of advertising that promote in society "goods" of mass demand - social policy [Dmitrieva, 2009]. Thus, social advertising borders on economics, sociology, psychology, philosophy, biology, and other sciences. The main misunderstanding that arises when interpreting the term "social advertising" is that the term "social" is too ambiguous to have a precise definition, and the term "advertising" is too commercial, in our understanding. [Ushkvarok, 2012].

Developed countries have communication strategies to solve social problems, creating a single concept of social advertising that allows you to operate effectively in the field of communication. In the Ukrainian information space, social advertising occupies an important place, developing as a separate area of advertising [Agarkov, 2013]. An important factor in social advertising is the formation of public opinion. Public opinion in civil society is an important factor in development, because it is in it that the idea of legitimacy (or illegitimacy) of power is enshrined. Public opinion is a summary not only of a certain social structure, but also of the historical and cultural experience of a certain society [Yermakova, 2011]. Currently, in Ukraine, there is no single concept for the development of social advertising, but there are private companies, NGOs and some public figures who deal with this issue. Public opinion is formed under the influence of media holdings that pursue their own goals and completely ignore socially important issues, preferring other types of advertising communication. In addition, the self-regulation of society allows you to unite on different social platforms and cover these issues yourself. Currently, the national information space raises issues on combating the coronavirus, discrimination against internally displaced persons, domestic violence, gender inequality, promoting the idea of mutual assistance and support for people in difficult life circumstances, combating drug and alcohol abuse and more. Within the country, social advertising also allows you to maintain an identity by showing interest in socially important issues of the population. V.V. Uchenova believes that social advertising is one of the most important tools of information policy and therefore is one of the most active tools for rapid response and pragmatic action in solving social problems of the country [Uchenova, 2006].

Social advertising depends on the social demand for coverage of universal problems. Such problems, due to their prevalence, become public, which in turn gain some "unannounced" support among other categories of the population. Agarkov O. emphasizes that in the information society, social advertising aims to promote, instill certain values, ideals and lifestyles, influencing people's behavior and changes in mass consciousness and perception of social phenomena [Agarkov, 2013].

The social demand is formed on the basis of popular conflict situations, such as the recent issue of combating domestic violence. The problem existed before, but was most popular during the pandemic, quarantine conditions, when people are forced to stay at home for a long time, which became a condition for the problem to recur. Due to the spread, the problem became public, which in turn led to a number of social advertisements and campaigns related to combating domestic violence. Thus, we observe that in society there is a social demand to solve this problem.

An important effect of social advertising is to increase the level of consolidation and trust around a particular issue. Social advertising integrates, creates new and strengthens existing links between social groups. Trust in information that can negatively affect recipients significantly increases the level of socialization of

people around information. L. Khavkina notes that social advertising has much greater trust of recipients, as it does not potentially predict bias and commercial effect, so it does not cause a standard psychological barrier in the perception of advertising [Khavkina, 2010]. Compared to commercial advertising, social advertising is more likely to avoid conscious and unconscious blocking by the recipient, as it has no commercial effect. This technique is a universal marker of high perception of advertising by the target audience. Social advertising, as I. Davydkina notes, in contrast to commercial, forms an idea not about the product, but about a specific social problem, ways to solve it, models of socially useful and socially safe behavior. Thus, social advertising contains motivation for socially useful action [Davydkina, 2009]. Nowadays, social advertising is becoming an information and communication phenomenon, as a tool of pedagogical and educational activities of society, as well as an important means of forming a mature society.

Due to the publicity of the disclosure of problems, and the way to solve them, society responds to the message in a certain way, changing the attitude of each individual, which in the mass plane can lead to mass change and action. Thus, a person identifies himself or his loved ones with a group that is able to fall into the conflict sphere of influence or already exists there, thereby responding to the situation. Initially, a person accepts information, changes his worldview about the problem or opposes it, and then shows a reaction. If the problem requires a change of attitude or certain actions, if it takes a minimum number of active audience - they form a general public attitude to the problem. If he does not accept - the problem will continue to exist. On a mass scale, the problem can unite people, which motivates them to action, but due to lack of awareness of the problem, leads to rejection in society. For example, as a result of active social advertising against Covid-19, at the beginning of the pandemic, people did not accept the reality of the virus and ignored the rules of personal protection. Wearing a mask meant showing oneself as a patient who was not accepted by society, as a result of which coronavirus infection was not taken seriously at the beginning of the pandemic, which led to a sharp increase in infections. As a result of constantly informing the public about social advertising, the active minority has introduced the habit of wearing masks in public places, which has now become the norm, thus reducing the level of those infected. The plasticity of society requires the active actions of an active minority, which is why social advertising is designed to motivate constant influence, for the benefit of solving social problems.

Social advertising is based on the principles of cognitive and psychological characteristics. During the construction, attention is paid to the content of the message, the target audience, a number of psychological characteristics and the method of its transmission. The task of the message is to be completely clear and to convey the correct content. It is important to understand the needs and ways of thinking of another person and to speak to them in one language. However, social adver-

tising messages are usually shocking or humorous, appealing to emotions of fear and pleasure, which is ideally directed to the emotional center of the individual's reactions. In his study, T. Sidorenko compared the perception of young people to shocking and humorous advertising and stressed that shocking social advertising significantly reduces the well-being, activity and mood of young people, i.e. his psychophysiological state, but most significantly affects the mood of the researcher. It is most appropriate to use the technique of shock in social advertising when it is designed to stop, destroy a certain stereotype of behavior (eg, anti-alcohol advertising), because such a powerful suppression of psychophysiological state of the body inhibits any manifestations of behavioral activity, including positive [Sidorenko, 2015].

Social advertising affects the social well-being of society, thanks to the consolidating function and highlighting the right reactions to existing problems, a group of people creates the concept of collective care and responsibility for the actions of others. This creates an occasion to create people's lives in a conflict-free environment. Russian researcher O. Grubin emphasizes that the subject of such advertising is an idea that has a certain social value, and in the long run can create new social values [Grubin, 2009]. At the cultural and moral level, social advertising shows acceptable and unacceptable things that exist in society. For example, a civilized person understands that such things as violence against the weak, anti-Semitism, xenophobia, bullying, etc., are examples of antisocial behavior and are unacceptable in society. With the achievement of globalization, new concepts such as racism, intolerance, etc. are added to the list of unacceptable things. According to T. Shalman, "the goal of social advertising is achieved by creating advertising appeals, which promote a positive phenomenon or talk about the consequences of negative habits and phenomena" [Shalman, 2014]. Therefore, providing examples of positive and negative phenomena of human coexistence in society is an active factor in the educational function of social advertising, which has a positive impact on society.

Man is a social being. Socialization requires a degree of altruism to achieve the goals of a group of people. As a result of conflict situations, a group of people can actively influence another, which can limit their rights, freedoms, preferences, and so on. In order for groups not to have a detrimental effect on other social groups, social advertising is one of the ways to level these conflicts, resolve them through publicity and change the mood of society, and so on. Encouraging the discussion of problems, creating a dialogue, disseminating information about the views of both parties encourages to show a civilized solution to problematic situations in society. Thus, social advertising creates a single information background that highlights the problem and shows ways to solve it.

In the case of new problematic issues of society related to human behavior, a new reason is created to resolve this social issue. A person's behavior depends on the circumstances in which he is and lives. If society does not adopt certain norms of behavior, and their violation is controlled, in all probability, a person will not

violate them. However, in other special circumstances, if a person is able to violate them for his own benefit, it is likely that he will do so. As a result of such a system of control, a person learns something new and at the same time seeks opportunities to break the control system with impunity for his own benefit. There are people who go for it consciously and understand the responsibility of their actions. Due to changes in conditions, rules, social reality, a person is in a changing state, adapting differently to others. As a result, people live in separate realities, but when they interact, they create common relationships and conflict situations, which they resolve with each other over time. This process is carried out cyclically, due to the development of society. If the problem is not resolved for some time and is massive and if society is unable to resolve this conflict arbitrarily, it is rooted in social reality. That is why it is necessary to involve effective communication and a solution strategy - social advertising. The effectiveness of communication directly depends on the public's trust in the source of advertising. They are public authorities, civic institutions, non-profit and private organizations. Effectiveness also depends on a lack of information about a particular problem. Due to poor awareness, alternative explanations appear in the form of conspiracy theories, fakes and messages with motivated benefits in favor of the addressee.

The big disadvantage of social advertising is its unpredictability. Since advertising on social topics has strategic goals focused on long-term action, the formation of sustainable and long-term behavior, the results may not appear immediately, but, for example, in a few years or even in the next generation. But given the high level of perception of this type of advertising, we can assume that it is the most effective in terms of long term.

By creating the necessary incentives and patterns of behavior, social advertising becomes an important component of communicative activities of society. Thus, social advertising forms the worldview of a morally mature information society. In contrast to other tools such as social campaigns, flash mobs, social projects, local social services, cultural exchanges, etc., social advertising is more engaging as it acts globally and directly raises conflict issues instead of indirect influence.

It is proved that social advertising directly depends on the social needs of society, as it causes a corresponding active reaction from society. In terms of the development of processes in society, this type of dissemination of information is a factor in the development of society and its civilization. It is outlined that the information society exists in a constantly changing environment that requires a high level of plasticity from society. It has been proven that social advertising has a positive effect on the well-being of society due to the consolidation of society around defense issues.

Conclusions. Given the above characteristics of social advertising with the structure of communicative activity of society, we define social advertising as one

of the types of influential social-institutional and subject-subject communication, which contains the ideas of social equality and mutual understanding. Due to the active influence on public opinion, it is a powerful tool for adjusting public relations. Social advertising is characterized by social rules and methods of solving problems at all levels of society, which aims to form a common image of the existing problem and correct actions to change it. Existing in the communicative field of society, they act as a consolidator of groups of people, perform the function of socialization and increase the plasticity of society.

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